

CONDUCTANCE OF CALCIUM GLUCONATE SOLUTIONS

BY A. N. KAPPA AND INDRA DEVA ARYA

Conductivities of calcium gluconate solutions have been determined over the temperature range of 25° to 50° and the range of equivalent concentration 0.10 to 0.002. The ionic conductivities of the gluconate ion at different temperatures have been calculated. Square root of equivalent concentration plotted against equivalent conductivities give very good straight lines in dilute solutions but the slopes differ considerably from the calculated Onsager slopes.

The prominence attained by calcium gluconate in pharmacology and pharmaceutical industry calls for a thorough understanding of the physicochemical properties of the salt. In connection with other work in progress in this laboratory it became necessary to know the conductivities of calcium gluconate solutions. The only record we have been able to trace in literature is that of a few measurements by Jensen and Ungast (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1941, 9, 195). We have measured the conductivities of the salt over the temperature range of 25°-50° and in dilute solutions. The results are recorded in the present communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Pure calcium gluconate was subjected to recrystallisation thrice, the final purification being effected from solutions in conductivity water. Analysis of the compound showed it to be the monohydrate.

Conductivity water as well as solutions of the salt were prepared and preserved carefully. Conductivity measurements were carried out with precision equipment using a 1000 cycle symmetric A. C. The conductivity of the water used for the preparation of each solution was measured and the solvent correction applied. The cell constant was determined frequently and checked up. The thermostat maintained the requisite temperature constant within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The usual precautions have all been observed. Repeated measurements were made for each solution, the solution itself being prepared fresh for each measurement. We estimate the error in our measurements to be in the neighbourhood of $\pm 1\%$. Extra-ordinary accuracy is not therefore claimed for our results.

Table I gives the results of our measurements at different temperatures.

TABLE I

Equivalent conductivity.

Eq. concn.	25°.	30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.
0.10	28.64	33.05	38.18	40.18	44.17	50.85
0.05	37.36	42.54	50.04	54.98	60.72	68.24
0.02	51.05	59.00	68.36	69.35	78.20	88.90
0.01	57.48	64.98	72.72	81.47	88.20	102.20
0.005	66.82	73.20	81.68	91.52	99.38	114.98
0.002	72.85	80.20	90.05	102.00	109.65	127.00
0.001	76.53	84.20	94.10	106.70	115.00	132.80
0.0005	78.20	86.90	97.40	110.50	118.90	136.40
0.0002	80.70	89.45	100.20	113.50	124.40	139.55
	84.80	94.50	105.00	116.70	128.90	143.00

Our results at 25° differ considerably from those of Jensen and Ungast (*loc. cit.*).

Equivalent conductivities plotted against square root of eq. concentration even up to concentration of $0.01N$ give very good straight lines. This is rather surprising when we take into consideration the large variations in conductivities at all the temperatures, as we proceed from $c=0.01$ to 0.0002 , the increase amounting to near about 50%. This kind of variation is indicative of incomplete dissociation. The values Λ_{∞} in the bottom column of the table have been obtained by the graphical method extending the straight lines up to $\sqrt{c}=0$.

Table II contains the calculated values for the mobilities of gluconate ion at different temperatures. The values for the $\frac{1}{2}\text{Ca}^{++}$ mobilities have been taken from the work of Benson and Gordon on the conductance of CaCl_2 solutions (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, 13, 470). (The value for 50° was obtained by extrapolation).

TABLE II

	25°.	30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.
Λ_{∞} ..	84.80	94.50	105.0	116.70	129.90	143.00
$\Lambda_{\frac{1}{2}\text{Ca}^{++}}$	59.50	66.60	73.26	80.03	88.21	93.50
Gluconate ion	25.30	27.90	31.74	36.67	41.69	49.50
Onsager slope, calc.	158.7	177.5	199.7	217.6	244.00	268.00
Onsager slope, expt.	266	295	318	372	399	437

In an electrolyte, where the variation of conductivity with concentration in dilute solutions is great, there is hardly any justification in expecting agreement with Onsager equation. The figures in the last two horizontal rows are included, as the differences between the calculated values and observed values for Onsager slopes are very wide.

In Table III the ionic conductances of organic ions are compared with that of gluconate ion.

TABLE III

Ion.	No. of atoms.	Conduc. at 25°.	Ion.	No. of atoms.	Conduc. at 25°.
Formate	4	51.2	Butyrate	13	30.8
Acetate	7	38.3	Valerate	16	28.8
Propionate	10	34.3	Caproate	19	27.4
			Gluconate	25	26.5

The values for other ions are taken from Landolt's Tables.